

Efficacy Of Clotrimazole Powder In Preventing Dermatological Complications Underneath Orthopedic Casts: A Comparative StudyAyush Gupta¹, Mayank Poddar², Shiv Chouksey³, Deepak Chaudhary⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Arthroscopy and Sports Medicine, BLK-Max Hospital, Pusa Road, Rajendra Place, New Delhi²Consultant Department of Arthroscopy and Sports Medicine, BLK-Max Hospital, Pusa Road, Rajendra Place, New Delhi.³Senior Consultant, Department of Arthroscopy and Sports Medicine BLK-Max Hospital⁴Principal Head Department of Arthroscopy and Sports Medicine, BLK-Max Hospital, Pusa Road, Rajendra Place, New Delhi

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ayush Gupta

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** POP Casts that are placed or applied for fractures and immobilisation. Throughout and following period during which casts are applied and after removal - cutaneous discomfort, itching, pain, and malodor are frequent, particularly in warm and damp surroundings. Clotrimazole is a synthetic imidazole with a broad spectrum of antimycotic activity.**Methodology:** A total of 60 patients were recruited with fractures of various parts of body such as of the distal radius, tibia, radio-ulnar shaft, as well as other limb components. The patients were included sequentially and divided into two groups: the Control group (n=30) and the Experimental group (n=30). A predesigned structured proforma was designed for the study which included the demographic profile of the patient, type of fracture experienced by the patient, type of cast placed, and positive or negative KOH prep test. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS (version 21.0) software. A level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.**Results:** Among 60 individuals with fractures, the control group included 21 (70 %) male patients and 9 (30 %) female patients, whereas the experimental group had 18 (60 %) male patients and 12 (40 %) female patients. The control group's average age was 31 years, whereas the experimental group's average age was 28 years. The most common site of fracture was the forearm in both control (63.33%) and experimental groups (50%). The KOH staining test of the skin scrapings of the patients in the control group and experimental group revealed significant differences in positive KOH staining**Conclusions:** The alteration of skin texture and color following cast placement was discovered to be due to the development of mycotic infection underneath the cast which was identified with a positive KOH staining test. The application of clotrimazole powder before cast placement was associated with better skin conditions than skin conditions without applying clotrimazole powder.**Keywords:** KOH Staining, Clotrimazole, Casting.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Immobilization of injured limbs has been performed for thousands of years. By far the most frequent intervention for limb fractures is cast immobilization. Casting is the mainstay of treatment as it provides more effective immobilization. [1-2] It is cheap and easy to apply, and can easily be molded to the desired shapes and contours of the body.

The medical literature reports that cast placement is used in approximately thirty-four % of overall fractures. It can be used not only for the treatment of fractured bones but also supports sprained ligaments, and inflamed and infected soft tissues.

However, they are considerably challenging to place and less merciful throughout the acute inflammatory phase, as well as having a significant potential for complications. [3-4] throughout and following casting, cutaneous discomfort, itching, pain, and malodor are frequent, particularly in warm and damp surroundings.

This progresses to compartment syndrome, heat wounds, cutaneous infection, pressure wounds, dermatitis, and joint rigidity. Children and adults have developed xerosis, hypertrichosis, cutaneous degeneration, and ulcerations as a result of cast placement. [5-9] Clotrimazole is a synthetic

imidazole with a broad spectrum of antimycotic activity. This FDA-approved drug is used to treat oral candidiasis, vaginal candidiasis, and dermatomycoses. It is also effective in the treatment of skin infections such as athlete's foot, jock itch, ringworm, pityriasis Versicolor, intertrigo, and erythrasma. [10] The topical treatment of clotrimazole is beneficial in treating cutaneous infections which are induced by dermatophytes or candida. In addition, clotrimazole has some activity against certain gram-positive bacteria, and at very high concentrations, has activity against *Trichomonas* spp. [11]

Wetting the cast in the days following its insertion may cause mold to grow over the skin underneath the cast, resulting in additional skin issues such as skin color changes, blister development, and acute itching. This study evaluated the skin scrapings collected after removing the cast, to identify the causative organism and the effect of clotrimazole powder in reducing changes occurring in the skin in terms of the presence of color change, skin lesions, pruritus, skin dryness, and skin cracking in patients with cast immobilization. [6-8]

Materials and Methods

Methodology: This present cross-sectional single-center comparative research was executed from the Orthopaedic ward of Pt. B. D.Sharma Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences (PGIMS), Rohtak, Haryana, using both clinical assessment and semi-structured, prevalidated questionnaire. Approval was sought from the institutional Biomedical Research Ethics Committee (BREC), Pt. B. D. Sharma PGIMS, UHS, Rohtak, and the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki were followed. From October 2022 till January 2024, Patients aged 18 years and above, having no major illness or skin condition, who did not take any other medication to alleviate skin condition, and gave signed a consent form were recruited. Patients with pre-existing skin conditions, such as eczema, having a history of clotrimazole or formulation components allergy or hypersensitivity, and having a background of psychosis or tried to commit suicide were excluded

Using N master sample size Software (version 2.0) and the data of the pilot study of two patients and the formula of Two Proportion - Hypothesis Testing - Large Proportion - Equal Allocation, a minimum of 24 sample sizes was required in each group.

Table 1:

Two Proportion - Hypothesis Testing - Large Proportion - Equal Allocation	
Proportion in group I	0.6
Proportion in group II	0.3
Estimated risk difference	0.3
Power (1- beta) %	80
Alpha error (%)	10
1 or 2 sided	1
The required sample size for each arm	24

Based on the calculated Proportion, 10% level of precision, 95% confidence level, and 80% power of the study. A total of 60 patients were recruited with fractures of the distal radius, tibia, radio-ulnar shaft, as well as other limb components. The patients were included sequentially and their categorization was determined based on the day of admission (odd and even) into two groups: the Control group (n=30), in which no clotrimazole application

was employed before cast placement, and the Experimental group (n=30), in which clotrimazole powder was applied before cast placement. A pre-designed structured proforma was designed for the study which included the demographic profile of the patient, type of fracture experienced by the patient, type of cast placed, and positive or negative KOH prep test. The classification of dry skin was done into normal, mild, moderate, and severe.

<i>Classification</i>	<i>Signs and Symptoms</i>
Tendency for dry skin	Clear
Mildly dry skin	Rough and/or scaling (+) No or mild itching (– or +) No pain (–) No or minimal erythema (– or +) No fissures (–)
Moderately dry skin	Rough and moderate scaling (++) Mild or moderate itching (+ or ++) Mild or moderate pain (+ or ++) Mild erythema (++) May have fissures (– or +)
Severely dry skin	Rough and severe scaling (+++) Severe itching (+++) Severe pain (+++) At least mild erythema (++) May have fissures (– or + to +++)

– = not present; + = mild; ++ = moderate; +++ = severe.

Treatment Procedure

The customary casting procedure was followed in the control group. In the experimental group, clotrimazole powder was applied to the skin area that was about to be sealed. Cotton stockinettes were draped around the region to be plastered which acted like a protective sleeve next to the skin. After that, cotton undercast padding was added. The cotton padding was subsequently put above the POP cast, which was subsequently shaped to suit the fracture site. Post-operative instructions were given to the patients. The cast was placed for a minimum of 45 days after which data was collected. A small scraping from the skin underneath the cast was sent to the dermatology department for the KOH prep test.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21, IBM Inc.

Descriptive data (Frequency distribution) was reported for each variable. The Chi-square test will be used for categorical variables. A level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Among 60 individuals with fractures, the control group included 21 (70 %) male patients and 9 (30 %) female patients, whereas the experimental group had 18 (60 %) male patients and 12 (40 %) female patients.

The control group's average age was 31 years, whereas the experimental group's average age was 28 years. The most common site of fracture was the forearm in both control (63.33%) and experimental groups (50%). The most common type of cast applied was short arm in both controls (50%) and experimental (43.33%) groups with a long leg cast applied the least number of times as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Representing Location of Fracture and Type of Cast Placed

	Control (n=30)	Experimental (n=30)
Location of fracture	P=0.108, ns	
Forearm	19 (63.3%)	15 (50%)
Tibia	5 (16.67%)	8 (26.7%)
Foot	6 (20%)	7 (23.4%)

Type of cast placed	P=0.538,ns	
Short arm	15 (50%)	13 (43.7%)
Short leg	7 (23.3%)	9 (30%)
Longarm	5 (16.6%)	4 (13.3%)
Long leg	3 (10%)	4 (13.3%)

Chi-square test, level of significance set at $p < 0.05$, Ns: non-significant, sig: significant

The KOH staining test of the skin scrapings of the patients in the control group revealed 18 (60%) positive skin scrapings for fungal infection, but a significantly lower number of 9 (30%) skin scrapings from the experimental group revealed positive KOH staining ($p=0.009$). Table 3

Table 3: Representing the Results of KOH Staining

	Control (n=30)	Experimental (n=30)
Positive	18 (60%)	9 (30%)
Negative	12 (40%)	21 (70%)
p-value	0.009*, sig	

Chi-square test, level of significance set at $p < 0.05$, Ns: non-significant, sig: significant

Significant differences in the findings of the skin were seen at follow-up ($p=0.026^*$, sig). After the cast was removed, 18 (60%) of the patients in the control group had dry skin, while only 9 (30%) of the patients in the experimental group had dry skin. Thirteen (72.22 %) of the patients in the control

group were defined as mildly dry, while five (27.77 %) were classified as moderately dry, with no patient experiencing severely dry skin. All of the patients presenting with dry skin from the experimental group were classified as mild dryness as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Category of skin dryness of skin in fungal-infected patients

Figure 2:

Discussion

Casts are frequently applied for routine orthopedic treatment for many acute fractures. The period of immobilization varies according to the patient and the fracture. It is usually administered for short periods to limit its complications. These plaster cast complications describe joint stiffness, muscle atrophy, cartilage degradation, ligament weakening, and disuse osteoporosis. [12] Skin complications such as ulceration occur where there is insufficient padding over bony protuberances and excoriation is known to occur particularly in casts worn by children who have become soiled. Skin atrophy and hyperpigmentation also occur. [3-4] The purpose of this research was to assess skin scraping after cast placement and to assess the effects of clotrimazole powder on modifications in skin texture after cast placement.

In the present study, following a KOH staining test of the skin scraping underneath the cast, 18 (60%) patients from the control group and only 9 (30%) patients from the experimental group were discovered positive, signifying the emergence of fungal infection beneath the cast following

application ($p < 0.05$). these Findings are suggestive of the fact that transmission of airflow is restricted beneath the semi- or impermeable cast substance, and sweat droplets cannot rapidly dissipate through the encased skin. Wetness, body oil, bacteria, and fungus proliferate and this enhanced growth may contribute to skin issues as well. [11] Furthermore, during the evaluation of skin dryness according to the criterion established before conducting the study, 18 (60%) of the control group patients were found to have dry skin after separation of the cast, whereas only 9 (30%) of the experimental group patients were encountered to have dry skin after removal of the cast. These findings indicate the effectiveness of clotrimazole powder in preventing the development of fungal infection within the cast. It works largely by disrupting the fungal cytoplasmic membrane's permeability barrier. It reduces ergosterol production in a concentration-dependent fashion by blocking 14 alpha lanosterol demethylation. The cell would not generate a functioning and intact cell membrane once ergosterol production is inhibited. It stimulates the development of mycotic cells which resulted in reduced skin lesions and less irritation in patients

having casts. In line with the above findings, Maganji M et al, among thirty-one patients had given 1 ibuprofen along with 1 placebo plaster simultaneously and assessed the extent of adherence and cutaneous irritancy.

Following twenty-one days of application, the findings revealed that the ibuprofen-coated plaster exhibited a decreased proportion of Grade 1 (23.3 % vs. 46.7 %, respectively), Grade 2 (10 % vs. 20 %), and Grade 3 (3 % vs. 16.1 %) irritancy ratings than the placebo. [13] Mak MF et al, also stated that calamine-treated children were less prone to developing skin lesions (1 vs. 9, odds ratio [OR]=0.115, p=0.009), itch less while casting (mean difference=0.74, p0.0001), seemed to have a larger drop in itch intensity (mean difference=0.84, p0.0001), and perspire less (p=0.048) as compared to noncalamine patients. [14]

One of the limitations of the study is that cutaneous changes are an objective end indicator. Additionally, because the cast specialists were never blindfolded, their casting techniques might have varied slightly. We did not take into account any additional factors that might have affected the outcomes (such the patient's level of physical activity or the temperature). The inability to count the number of fungal growth in the skin scraping, which may have allowed for a more precise evaluation of the effectiveness of the clotrimazole powder, is another drawback of the study. [15-16]

Conclusion

The development of a mycotic infection beneath the cast, which was detected with a positive KOH staining test, was found to be the cause of the change in skin texture and colour after cast implantation. When clotrimazole powder was applied before to casting, skin conditions were found to be better than they would have been otherwise.

References

- Ekwall A, Carlberg E, Palmberg G, Sloberg R. An audit of complications of fiberglass cast and hybrid cast for fractures of the foot, ankle and forearm in a Swedish emergency department. *Int J Orthop Trauma Nurs* 2018; 31:32-4.
- Meling T, Harboe K, Søreide K. Incidence of traumatic long-bone fractures requiring in-hospital management: A prospective age- and gender-specific analysis of 4890 fractures. *Injury* 2009; 40:1212-9.
- DiFazio R, Vessey J, Zurakowski D, Hresko MT, Matheney T. Incidence of skin complications and associated changes in children treated with hip spica casts for femur fractures. *J Pediatr Orthop* 2011; 31:17-22.
- DiFazio RL, Harris M, Feldman L, Mahan ST. Reducing the incidence of cast-related skin complications in children treated with cast immobilization. *J Pediatr Orthop* 2017; 37:526-31.
- DiPaola MJ, Abzug JM, Pizzutillo PD, Herman MJ. Incidence and etiology of unplanned cast changes for fractures in the pediatric population. *J Pediatr Orthop* 2014;34:643-6
- Woo TE, Somayaji R, Haber RM, Parsons L. Diagnosis and Management of Cutaneous Tinea Infections. *Adv Skin Wound Care*. 2019 Aug; 32(8):350-357. [PubMed]
- Kalra MG, Higgins KE, Kinney BS. Intertrigo and secondary skin infections. *Am Fam Physician*. 2014 Apr 01; 89(7):569-73. [PubMed]
- Haley CA, DeJong ES, Ward JA, Kragh JF Jr. Waterproof versus cotton cast liners: a randomized, prospective comparison. *Am J Orthop (Belle Mead NJ)* 2006; 35:137-40.
- Ale I, Lachapelle JM, Maibach HI. Skin tolerability associated with transdermal drug delivery systems: an overview. *Adv Ther*. 2009; 26 (10):920-935.
- Khatter NJ, Khan MAB. Clotrimazole. [Updated 2022 Jul 11]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan-.
- Ghannoum MA, Rice LB. Antifungal agents: mode of action, mechanisms of resistance, and correlation of these mechanisms with bacterial resistance. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. 1999 Oct; 12(4):501-17.
- Halanski M, Noonan KJ. Cast and splint Immobilization: complications. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg*. 2008; 16:30-40.
- Maganji M, Connolly MP, Bhatt A. Cutaneous irritancy of an ibuprofen medicated plaster in healthy volunteers. *Postgrad Med [Internet]*. 2018 [cited 2022 Feb 6]; 130(3):334-40. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29415606/>
- Mak MF, Li W, Mahadev A. Calamine lotion to reduce skin irritation in children with cast immobilisation. *J Orthop Surg (Hong Kong) [Internet]*. 2013; 21(2):221-5. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/230949901302100222>
- Chan Y, Selvaratnam V, Garg N. A fungating spica. *BMJ Case Rep [Internet]*. 2015 [cited 2022 Feb 6]; 2015(jan21 1):bcr2014206901-bcr2014206901. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/labs/pmc/articles/PMC4307088/>
- Halanski M, Noonan KJ. Cast and splint Immobilization: complications. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg*. 2008; 16:30-40.